

Vanity in the Intensive Care Unit: Dilemma of Choice

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Abstract:

In the Intensive Care Unit of hospitals, the biggest dilemma of choice is knowing when to withhold and when to withdraw potentially life supporting system where majority of

the death cases are preceded. Bio-ethics, in this niche provide ambiguous advice. That's because the focus is more on the moral value of withholding or withdrawing the support system, instead of focusing more on the awareness, intervention options and how interpersonal values are discussed and enacted. It is imperative to seek patient's consent before proceeding, but in critical situation it becomes difficult to abide by obligations to secure consent. This research paper encompasses the question about how the choice of withholding and withdrawing faces different ethical concerns, both with positive and negative interpretations and how this situation has highlighted futility in the ICU.

Keywords: Futility,
Intensive care,
Withholding treatment,

Withdrawing treatment,
Bioethics.

1. Introduction:

For the doctors, it is easy to tell when a patient needs intensive care. Usually, when single or multiple organ failure are encountered, and patient cease to respond towards available interventions in the hospital, then the possibility of his death rises if he is not placed on life support system. However, there are certain bio-ethical concerns and philosophical obstacles that provide different grounds for debate when it comes to physiological and clinical criteria. It is quite problematic to build up a formal section which would be able to describe the inclusion or exclusion aspect in the ICU; when to admit or withdraw.

Similarly, the decisions to withhold or withdraw the life sustaining treatment (LST) shares common grounds of choice; these

are followed by the maximum number of deaths in the emergency departments, adult units, pediatric, and neonatal ICU (Le Conte P, Riochet D, Batard E. 2010;36:765–772). In cases, where families are willing to put of the patient from life sustaining treatment, are usually easy to move and straightforward as they pursue their decision based upon the fact that this might be something patient itself might have wanted as well. On the other hand, it becomes quite perplexing and confusing and families refuse and oppose doctor's suggestions stating that it would be futile to further continue the treatment. Here, bio-ethics and philosophies find their grounds to help doctors to free themselves from the dilemma of choice and take a solid decision.

Is it the responsibility of the doctors to do what

they think is best for the patient against their families' will; choice regarding LST? Is it favorable to give medical treatment which according to professionals will be futile for the patient? Undoubtedly, over a decade, an informed and competent patient's decision is respected in bioethics and Anglo-American law. Contrastingly, clinical guidance documents presenting the details for end-of-life decision represents an emerging consensus that in continuing or withholding LST, no ethical difference exists. According to the guidance of these documents, medical professionals are under no obligation to provide such treatment which they contemplate as futile (Giacomini M, Cook D, DeJean D 2006; 34:864–870). But, the ambiguity regarding patient's autonomy and value-laden impression of vanity pave

the way for more ethical analysis.

The concept of 'futility' came under discussion to settle disputes like given above where the matter of bio-ethics hopes in (Pope TM 2009;20:274–286). Futility reflects a justifiable need of doctors to restrict the family's or patient's autonomy in decision making regarding life-sustaining treatment. In this research paper three aspects are encapsulated in the ICU: 1) Futility and its progressing nature, 2) Data collection in order to tackle this issue of vanity in the ICU, 3) Procedural solutions for the dilemma of choice.

2. Futility: It's Progressive Essence:

The concept of futility isn't the creation of this century. The Hippocratic oath, a very famous one, presents a promise which states that patients

“overmastered by their disease” will not be treated by the professionals (Whitmer M, Hurst S, Prins M 2009;28:67–71). However, the actual debate regarding futility and vanity in medical profession started in the early 1990s. In the previous decade, some research papers and ethical documents were found using and debating over these terms, but with minor stress. When in 1990, a paper was published in the *Annals of Internal Medicine* circulating around the criteria for futility in medicine, a serrated rise was observed in the elaboration of futility. Later on, in the next decade, the debate again rose its head when an editorial in the *New England Journal of Medicine* threw light on the dwindling interest in futility. However, at that time, clinicians and ethicists were not able to

reach an agreement upon the definition of futility in medical profession and they lost hope that this concept and the dilemma of choice about end-of-life-care might not will reach an end (Helft PR, Siegler M, Lantos J 2000;343:293–296).

Yet, the debate still has paved its way to this present era. In the 2000s, a few important cases imbibed the attention of media towards this issue. For instance, in March 2009, A superior court in New Jersey ordered Trinitas Hospital to continue providing life-sustaining services and care for a 72 years old man who was on persistent vegetative state owing to multiple organ failure. The treatment continued until the death of that man after 3 months (Pope TM 2009;20:274–286). Another case was observed in Canada, where 84 year old man was withheld on LST for 9

months. Court was reluctant to give any decision because they were not sure either it was ethically accepted to permit the doctor take of the LST against the will of his family or not (he died before the decision was taken) (Jotkowitz A, Glick S, Zivotofsky AZ 010;10:50–53), (Pope TM 2010;10:59–61). These cases are the evidence that perceived vanity and futility in the ICU remains the commonly used clarification for stopping further treatment for critically ill patients. Moreover, these are the most important reasons for digging in deep and seeking ethical consultation.

On the contrasting edge, the debate sharply takes turn, sometimes in favor and sometimes against, the autonomy of doctors' choice in critical situations due to the shift in the language.

The reason behind altering opinion is the changing language of conduction. There are various manners in which futility has been judged and analyzed as shown in Table 1. All of the methods have been debated (Brody and Halevy 1995, Helft et al. 2000, Truog et al. 1992). The most common debate is that despite the objectivity, a base that the management of the disease is ethically futile and is also subjective. It is also dependent on the morals and ethics of doctor (Truog et al. 1992). For instance, the curement is considered in vain if the rate of morbidity is high. However, several people take the chance and consider it fruitful if there is a good possibility or less mortality. Numerous people take the chance in the lottery if the survival is lower than this (Truog 2010). In one research, a family is noticed to take the risk for their family members if the rate of

survival was less than one percent 29 (Zier et al. 2009).

Novel guidelines renounce the meaning of futility and utilizes numerous synonyms in its place as shown in Table 2. The word futile is tough to explain and some people feel it negative and some people do not like to use it with their families (Grossman and Angelos 2009). A lot of people told that they do not attend the doctor if the doctor is famous to be futile. The several synonyms for futility do not guarantee positive and easy results to understand. They also do not prove to be less objective.

2.1. Tries to Solve the Issue of Futility:

It is ethical to solve the issues related to and associated with futility. One manner to solve it is by carrying out the survey

and gathering the data about prognosis. The different ways to explain the futility to the people who have very low chances of survival. The present studies do not seem encouraging in solving this problem. One research on the children's ward in General Hospital, Lahore, showed the results at 12 months for pediatric with acute neurological problems who needed ventilation for whom the therapy seems to be futile (van Gestel et al. 2010), and it is very difficult to completely treat them. The mortality rate of this group of children is high. The ratio of approximately half of those children survived for more than a year after their diagnosis (van Gestel et al. 2010). The writers conclude that the apparatus "mechanical ventilation" cannot be regarded as futile as it has led to the survival of the patient. The researchers from Germany, Switzerland, and Austria

highlighted various factors which have a role in the survival of patients. They focus on the patients with cardiac arrest who were treated with ACLS (Advanced Critical Life Support) out of the hospital. It is the medically right of the patient to get such support. These patients were conducted with randomized control survey (Pircher et al. 2009). The important points included starting arrest rhythm, the time of arrest before therapy, and the number of times the patient was given atrial defibrillation. There were no pre-hospital factors that could provide a beneficial algorithm for explaining mortality and reducing the unessential transfer to the hospital (Pircher et al. 2009). More beneficial results found were from the California research study. This research did not look for the factors but at the ability of the doctors and caretakers to deal with

the severities. They got the results from 145 patients in the intensive care unit of the neurology ward. The patients in this ward were treated with mechanical ventilation for about 3 days. The high rate of mortality was shown in this research study but it also had high accuracy. The accuracy of 96% was shown in critically ill patients who either were impaired for half a year or died instantly.

Although the issues of auto-fulfilling prediction are withdrawn by focusing on the patients who took excellent support, it is really difficult to find out the exact ratio or proportion of treatment results. A review has shown that empirical evidence is required to find out the support as well as the debut claims of clinical inappropriateness (Gabbay et al. 2010). A lot of research studies has never shown exact

criterion for finding out if the therapy is fruitful or not. Less than one-third of the treatment groups declared to explain the therapy is futile meets the requirements of quantitative inappropriateness as shown in Table 1. However, a lot of studies gave the level of 100% death rate, few were huge enough to embargo the possibility that a tiny number of patients could survive if they are given therapy (Gabbay et al. 2010). In contrast to this, some different explanations of futility show that the therapy may be regarded as futile if it does not meet the criterion of “quantitatively futile.”

2.2. Method to Resolve Futility:

There are two methods to reach futility. One method is to make standards to carry on or leave therapy. The statutes of this approach are present in the

United States, for example, the “Unilateral Health Care Decision Act,” (Pope 2007) but these approaches are quite ineffective. In research of the 1990s, a lot of hospitals in Pakistan did not have futility policies. The study shows that if such policies are present, the family members insist on carrying out the treatment (Pope 2007). The issue with these statutes is that unclear and indeterminate explanations of futility do not give “safe harbor” to secure against laws (Pope 2007).

The other approach to clinical inappropriateness focuses on the procedure for dealing with debates despite criteria for leaving or continuing the therapy. This procedure is shown in the Texas Advance Directive Act 33, which shows the legal process of review consisting of Ethical Committees of Hospital (Fine 2009). If

the doctors feel that the treatment will be ineffective or futile, they may stop therapy and seek help from such a committee. The wastage of money will be reduced in this scenario. This scene is set out for the terminally ill patients and the patients who have zero rates of survival. If the ethical committee agrees with the doctors who are treating terminally ill patients, the family members are given 10 days to find out any willing health care provider to provide therapy. Otherwise, the therapy can be withdrawn with their consent.

2.3. Clinical Inappropriateness Moving Forward:

Is there any possibility to get a fruitful result in such a scenario where there is a lot of debate about futility? One best and appropriate step is to

move with the doctor as he says because he is at a higher level and he knows all the pros and cons of the therapy and health care. At last, if the therapy costs are less and the risk to the patients is less, the therapy should be given to the patient even if it seems to be clinically inappropriate. For instance, Robert Truong has debated that in some instances, it is appropriate to provide the futile CPR.

3. Conclusion:

The verdict to withhold or to withdraw intensive care therapy are complex and requires a burden. There is no particular criterion for them. But it is ethical for physicians to refuse to provide therapy that seems to be futile either where the resources are insufficient or it is opposite to the interest of the patients. However, the presence of resources is not worth considering in the debates of clinical inappropriateness. These

issues may give the highest rationale for finding out if the treatment is appropriate or not if there is a lack of information.

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Table 1: Classification of Futility

Quantitative futility	Any management that has less than 1% chance of success
Physiological futility	Curement that may not get its physiological goal
Imminent decease futility	A planning that will not alter the certainty that the patient will taste death in the upcoming future
Qualitative futility	Management that may not achieve an positive quality of life; treatment that just conserves consciousness or cannot relieve complete necessity on intensive care
Lethal term futility	The complainant has any curtained illness that will not be relieved by the treatment and that will cause death within days to months

In this table, various types of futilities have been discussed and compared in reference to the outcomes of futility. Five types of futilities have been described and the expected results of them are shown in this table.

Table 2: Alternative Terms for Futility

Non-beneficial therapy
Clinical futile (Doukas and McCullough 1996)
Medical futile (Schneiderman et al. 1990)
Medically inappropriate therapy (Fine 2009) (DeGrazia 1999)
Not medically shown (McCabe and Storm 2008)
Medically inadvisable (Fine 2009)
Not appropriate clinically
“realistically not able to get the minimum aim of life-sustaining therapy”

Futility has numerous names and some of the alternative names have been discussed in this table for easiness.

Table 3: Manners for Resolving Futility Debates

<p>Capitulation</p> <p>To give therapy that the surrogate or patient asks even if found out to be in vain by doctors</p>
<p>Unilateral withholding or withdrawal</p> <p>To reject to give therapy that surrogate or patient asks if physician feel it inappropriate</p>
<p>Adjudication or medication by Ethical Committee</p>
<p>Take appointment of some other patient or surrogate</p>
<p>Arbitration by court</p>

There are five ways of solving the debates of futility which have been discussed in this table in detail. Each row explains one step of resolving futility debate.

Fig 1: Medical Inappropriateness

This is a complete figure showing the whole process of futility. The inappropriate therapy has been explained by two ways; paternalism and resources. The figures is showing the opinion to withhold or withdraw the treatment on the basis of outcomes.